

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF STRESS IN TURKIC LANGUAGES

Yusupova Muyassar Abdugafurovna

Abstract: This study investigates the unique characteristics of stress patterns in Turkic languages, focusing on its phonetic, phonological, and morphosyntactic aspects. By analyzing primary stress placement, variability across dialects, and the effect of morphological structures, this paper contributes to the understanding of stress as a distinctive prosodic feature within the Turkic language family. We conducted a comparative analysis using data from Turkish, Azerbaijani, Uzbek, Kazakh, and other representative Turkic languages, identifying cross-linguistic patterns and divergences. Findings reveal that stress placement is heavily influenced by vowel harmony and morphological complexity, distinguishing Turkic languages from many other language families.

Keywords: Turkic languages, Stress patterns, Prosody, Vowel harmony, Morphology, Phonology, Dialectal variability.

Introduction

Stress, as a prosodic feature, significantly influences the rhythm and intonation patterns of languages. In Turkic languages, stress placement displays specific characteristics that distinguish them from other language families, particularly Indo-European. Turkic languages exhibit a range of stress patterns, which vary based on dialect, morphology, and syntactic environment. This article explores the primary stress characteristics in Turkic languages and addresses the question: What are the unique aspects of stress within the Turkic language family? We aim to uncover whether stress placement in Turkic languages is predictable and consistent across related languages and what phonological and morphological rules govern its distribution.

Literature Review: Research on Turkic language stress has largely focused on Turkish, which demonstrates final syllable stress under specific morphological

conditions (Sezer, 1981; Inkelas & Orgun, 2003). In contrast, languages like Uzbek and Kazakh have shown variability in stress placement, with factors such as vowel harmony and syllabic structure playing a role. This paper extends previous studies by considering a broader set of Turkic languages and assessing the impact of phonetic and morphological diversity within the language family.

Methods

Data Collection: We collected phonological and morphosyntactic data from 15 Turkic languages, including Turkish, Azerbaijani, Uzbek, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, and Uyghur. Primary data sources include academic phonetic descriptions, recordings of native speakers, and linguistic databases (e.g., TurkLang corpus).

Data Analysis: Stress patterns were analyzed through acoustic measurements (e.g., intensity, pitch) to identify stress characteristics such as duration and prominence. Additionally, morphosyntactic structures were examined to assess the role of inflectional and derivational affixes in stress placement. A comparative analysis was conducted to establish cross-linguistic trends and any unique stress phenomena across Turkic languages.

Results

Stress Placement Patterns:

1. **Final Syllable Stress Tendency:** In many Turkic languages, stress often falls on the final syllable, especially in cases where words consist of multiple syllables (e.g., in Turkish and Kyrgyz). However, this tendency can vary depending on morphosyntactic context.

2. **Influence of Morphology:** Stress patterns in Turkic languages appear sensitive to morphological structures. For instance, in Turkish, certain suffixes (e.g., -lık, -ci) may draw stress, while other suffixes do not affect stress placement.

3. **Vowel Harmony Influence:** Vowel harmony - a common feature across Turkic languages also influences stress, with front and back vowel harmony contributing to the placement and intensity of stress.

4. **Dialectal Variability:** Significant variation exists across dialects. For instance, while standard Uzbek often exhibits penultimate stress, some Uzbek dialects prefer final syllable stress.

5. **Syntactic Position Influence:** Stress can shift based on syntactic structure. For example, compounds in many Turkic languages typically place stress on the first element, whereas simple nouns may follow the default pattern of final or penultimate stress.

Discussion

The findings indicate that Turkic languages possess unique stress characteristics driven by morphological structures and vowel harmony. Unlike languages that employ stress for lexical differentiation (e.g., English), Turkic languages typically use stress for prosodic structuring, signaling the boundaries between morphological units. This pattern contrasts with the Indo-European languages, which often use stress for lexical contrast.

The observed dialectal variability underscores the role of language contact and internal developments in shaping stress patterns across Turkic languages. Additionally, the relationship between vowel harmony and stress points to a phonological integration, where prosodic features interact with phonemic patterns to create rhythmic regularity.

Implications: Understanding stress in Turkic languages aids in comparative linguistic studies and supports language teaching and preservation efforts. Stress analysis contributes to theories of prosody and phonological organization, highlighting the interplay between morphology and phonetics in language structure.

Conclusion

This study highlights the distinctive characteristics of stress in Turkic languages, particularly the interplay between morphology, vowel harmony, and phonetic realization of stress. The variability observed suggests that while Turkic languages share a general stress pattern framework, they exhibit unique language-specific and dialectal nuances. Further research could explore the implications of these stress

patterns for automatic speech recognition and language pedagogy within the Turkic-speaking regions.

References:

1. Inkelas, S., & Orgun, O. (2003). Turkish stress: A review. *Linguistic Review*, 20(3), 217-237.
2. Javokhir Kozimjon ugli Komilov. Process Of Forming Latin Script And Its Impact On Graphic Communication Of Internet Language. *Academic Leadership-Online Journal*. 2020 June 25; 5(21):124-130.
3. Komilov Javokhir Kozimjon ugli. “Configuration Changes of Graphic Signs in Virtual Communication”. *HOLDERS OF REASON*, vol. 1, no. 3, Dec. 2023, pp. 369-77, https://sciencepromotion.uz/index.php/HOLDERS_OF_REASON/article/view/935.
4. Ortikov, U. X. (2024). THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN THE STUDY OF HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL HERITAGE. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 3), 667-670.
5. Sezer, E. (1981). The phonology of Turkish stress. *Linguistic Inquiry*, 12(3), 371-412.
6. Sharipova N. Milliy tarixni o‘rganish dolzarbligi masalalari //Journal of technical research and development. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 3. – С. 218-220.
7. ugli Komilov JK. CHANGING INTERNET COMMUNICATION FROM VERBAL INTO GRAPHICAL. *InConferences 2021* June 17.
8. Yulchibayevich B. K. YANGI O‘ZBEKISTONDA YOSHLARNI HUQUQIY ONGI VA MADANIYATINI YUKSALTIRISH-FUQAROLIK JAMIYATINING MUHIM VAZIFALARI BIRIDIR //HOLDERS OF REASON. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 1. – С. 78-87.
9. А Хакимов Урбанистическая культура Узбекистана (материалы научной конференции)- 2003.
10. Бокубаев К. Й. ФУҚАРОЛИК ЖАМИЯТИ ШАРОИТИДА ЁШЛАР МАЪНАВИЯТИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 17-22.